

SKIN-STRINGER SEPARATION IN GLARE COMPOSITE AEROSPACE PANELS

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SUMMARY

The separation of Glare[®] skin-stringer configurations for aerospace applications is investigated experimentally and analytically using fracture mechanics. Fatigue life curves are produced for two skin-stringer configurations. Predictions of the fatigue life are derived by using finite element modelling and utilising fatigue fracture data.

Keywords: Fibre Metal Laminate, Glare[®], Debonding, Fatigue, Fracture

INTRODUCTION

Glare[®] is a type of Fibre/Metal Laminate (FML) developed more than two decades ago. It comprises glass fibre reinforced epoxy layers sandwiched between aerospace grade aluminium layers and optimises the properties of both the FRPs and lightweight metals [1]. Glare[®] is one of the materials extensively used in the fuselage structure of the new Airbus A380.

Adhesive bonding has become a very promising process to replace traditional mechanical fastening methods in aerospace applications. A skin-stringer bonded construction provides enhanced compression stiffness and can be used as a primary load bearing structure. However, under the application of flexural loading, debonding or delamination may easily occur. The investigation of failure of CFRP composite bonded skin-stringer constructions has received extensive attention in the literature [2-4]. In the present work the debonding of Glare[®] skin-stringer configurations subject to fatigue loading is investigated experimentally and the fatigue life is predicted utilising fracture mechanics experimentally and numerically.

MATERIALS AND TEST PROCEDURES

Glare[®]

Two types of Glare[®] specimens were tested. The first type comprised Glare[®] HS skin and Glare[®] 3 Z type stringers. Glare[®] HS is similar to Glare[®] 3 but FM-906 epoxy is used instead of FM-94. The second type of specimens comprised Glare[®] 3 skin and stringers. The specimen types and material composition is given in Table 1.

Type I specimens were cut from a 800×600 mm² panel, which was supplied by Alenia Aeronautica. Three Z type stringers were bonded, using one layer of the Hysol[®] EA 9657 film adhesive, along the length of the panel. Specimens 185×20 mm were cut,

with the Z stinger in the middle along the length, using a band saw. Parallel edges were then polished using a flat belt grinder. Type II specimens were manufactured at MERL. A 200×20 mm piece of Glare[®] 3 was bonded by means of one layer of the film adhesive on a 200×185 mm flat sheet of Glare[®] 3. The adhesive was left to cure under light pressure for 90 min at 177 °C. Both types of specimens are shown in Figure 1.

Table 1 Specimen types and material composition

Specimens			Metal Layers	Fibre Layers ^a
Type I	Skin	Flat	Al 7475-T761 0.3 mm	FM-906-27%-S2 Glass-187-460
	Stringer	Z-type	Al 7475-T761 0.3 mm	FM-94-27%-S2 Glass-187-460
Type II	Skin	Flat	Al 7475-T761 0.3 mm	FM-94-27%-S2 Glass-187-460
	Stringer	Flat	Al 7475-T761 0.3 mm	FM-94-27%-S2 Glass-187-460

^a Orientation was 0/90 for all types of Glare[®] (i.e. Glare[®] 3 and Glare[®] HS)

Figure 1 Type I and Type II Glare[®] specimens

Quasi-static 3-point bending tests were performed on a number of specimens on a screw driven universal testing machine equipped with a 1 kN load cell. These tests were used as a guide for determining the conditions for fatigue testing and for verification of the finite element model. Strain gauges were applied to three Type I specimens to measure strains on the skin and the stringer during loading and dis-bonding. All tests were performed with a 80 mm span length and a constant crosshead displacement of 0.5 mm/min.

Figure 2 Experimental set-up for 3-pt bending fatigue testing

Fatigue tests under flexural loading (3-point bending) were performed on a servo-hydraulic testing machine. The experimental set-up is shown in Figure 2. All tests were performed with a span length of 80 mm and a frequency of 5 Hz. All tests for both Type I and type II specimens were performed in a displacement controlled mode with an applied displacement ratio of $\delta_{\min} / \delta_{\max} = 0.1$. Maximum applied displacements were chosen so as not to cause yielding of the aluminium layers during testing. The change in compliance of the specimens (linear fit of the force-displacement response) was monitored throughout the fatigue test on regular cycle intervals. The change in compliance was associated with the initiation and crack propagation along the bondline of the adhesive layer between the skin and the stringer.

Adhesive

A structural film adhesive Hysol[®] EA 9657 was used throughout this study. This is aluminium filled, fabric supported film adhesive with a nominal uncured thickness of 0.26 mm. The manufacturer's recommended cure cycle is 90 min at 177 °C.

Flat sheets with a nominal thickness of 2 mm were produced by curing 10 layers of adhesive under high hydrostatic pressure (20 bars). An existing method, to produce minimal porosity flat sheets of adhesives, was utilized [5]. Dumbbell shaped specimens were machined out of the sheets using a CNC machine and tensile tests were performed with a constant crosshead rate of 1 mm/min. Longitudinal and transverse strains, to obtain Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, were measured by means of strain gauges.

Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens were manufactured using 10 mm thick aluminium adherends (Al 6082). The thickness of the DCB arms was chosen to avoid plastic deformation during testing. Quasi-static tests under Mode I (peeling) loading were performed on a screw driven universal testing machine equipped with a 1 kN load cell. Specimens were loaded at a constant displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. The strain energy release rate for crack initiation (fracture toughness), G_{Ic} , as well as for crack propagation was evaluated.

Figure 3 (a) Mode I double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen and (b) Mixed Mode I/II flexural peel specimen (FPS)

In order to characterise the fatigue crack growth resistance of the film adhesive, Mode I (peel) and Mixed Mode I/II (peel/in-plane shear) tests were performed. For the Mode I test the DCB specimen was used while for the Mixed Mode I/II the Flexural Peel Specimen (FPS) was utilized (Figure 3). More details on these tests methodologies for

structural adhesives can be found elsewhere [6]. The measured Mixed Mode I/II strain energy release rate, $G_{I/II}$, from the FPS test comprised 57% Mode I, G_I , and 43% Mode II, G_{II} .

All tests were conducted on a servo-hydraulic multi-station test facility developed by MERL. Up to six specimens can be tested simultaneously in fatigue on this test frame. Six specimens were tested simultaneously under Mode I conditions at a frequency of 5 Hz. The fatigue test was performed under displacement controlled mode with an applied displacement ratio of $\delta_{\min} / \delta_{\max} = 0.1$. For linear elastic behaviour and small displacements the displacement ratio is equivalent to the load R -ratio. For the case of Mixed Mode I/II eight specimens were tested in pairs to produce the crack growth curve.

Table 2 Equations for the calculation of the strain energy release rate using a compliance calibration method

Loading Mode	Test Configuration	Compliance	$G_{I\max}$ or $G_{I/II\max}$
Mode I	DCB	$C^{1/3} = m(a + \Delta)$	$G_{I\max} = \frac{3P_{\max}\delta_{\max}}{2b(a + \Delta)}$
Mixed Mode I/II	FPS	$C = C_0 + ma^3$	$G_{I/II\max} = \frac{3ma^2P_{\max}^2}{2b}$

A compliance calibration method was used to derive the adhesive crack length, a , during fatigue from the monitored test specimen compliance, C . The relationship between compliance and crack length, known from simple beam theory, was established experimentally by testing specimens with different known crack lengths. The maximum cyclic strain energy release rate was then calculated from the equations in Table 2.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Adhesive Properties

The mechanical properties of the film adhesive derived from the tensile tests are given in Table 3. These properties were used to model the adhesive layer in the skin/stringer arrangements.

Table 3 Adhesive measured mechanical properties

Adhesive Hysol [®] EA 9657			
$E = 4.7$ GPa	$\nu = 0.34$	$\sigma_{ult} = 55$ MPa	$\epsilon_f = 2.5$ %

The fracture toughness of the film adhesive under Mode I loading was 579 ± 90 J/m². The fatigue crack growth resistance under both Mode I and Mixed Mode I/II is given in

Figure 4 in the form of crack growth rate, da/dN , vs. maximum cyclic strain energy release rate, G_{max} . A compliance calibration methodology was followed for the calculation of the crack growth and the values of G_{max} based on the equations in Table 1. The threshold cyclic strain energy release rate (no growth) for Mode I and Mixed Mode I/II loading conditions were found 165 J/m^2 and 159 J/m^2 , respectively. By extrapolating the linear part of the curves in Figure 4 to 10^{-7} mm/cycle the threshold values, G_{th} , were 118 J/m^2 and 62 J/m^2 for Mode I and Mixed Mode I/II, respectively. Under pure Mode I the crack growth curve was very steep, with the crack growth happening on a short range of $G_{I_{max}}$ values. The contribution of the Mode II component in the Mixed Mode I/II test found to slow the crack growth and lead to lower threshold values. The linear part of the fatigue crack growth resistance curves was fitted with Paris Law equation and the results of the fitting procedure are given in Table 4.

Figure 4 Fatigue crack growth resistance experimental curves for (a) Mode I and (b) Mixed Mode I/II loading. (Key: — Paris Law fit, — 95% prediction limits)

Table 4 Paris Law constants for Mode I and Mixed Mode I/II crack growth resistance curves

Paris Law		Mode I	Mixed Mode I/II
$da/dN = AG_{max}^B$	A	7.30×10^{-23}	5.39×10^{-16}
	B	7.30	4.62

Glare® Skin-Stringer Testing

The quasi-static tests results are summarized in Table 5. For Type I specimens fracture occurred in an unstable manner (rapid crack propagation after initiation) and always from one side of the Z stringer. For Type II specimens the crack initiated and

progressively propagated along the bond line. This happened at much higher loads compared to Type I specimens and from both sides of the flat stringer. The behaviour of both specimen types was linear up to fracture. Therefore, displacements were chosen for the fatigue tests within this linear region.

Table 5 Quasi-static experimental results for Type I and Type II specimens

	Specimen	Fracture Initiation Load [N]	Fracture Initiation Displacement [mm]	Skin Strain at Fracture Initiation [$\mu\epsilon$]	Stringer Strain at Fracture Initiation [$\mu\epsilon$]	Stiffness [N/mm]
Type I	A3	124	2.39	3125	1627	52.1
	B8	141	2.40			56.6
	B9	126	2.33	3212	1590	54.3
	B11	136	2.47			54.9
	C14	132	2.56			55.2
	C15	117	2.25	2995	1614	53.5
Type II	1.6	167	3.31			51.0
	1.7	170	3.39			50.9
	6	151	3.10			49.6
	7	146	3.05			48.6

Figure 5 Experimental data from 3-point bending fatigue tests for Type I and Type II specimens

Fatigue test results are presented, in analogy to an $S-N$ curve, as applied maximum displacement vs. number of cycles to failure (Figure 5). Final failure was defined as a total crack propagation of 3.3 mm or a crack area of 66 mm². This crack length can be detected using non-destructive inspection techniques. Moreover, for this crack length the aluminium layers of the Glare[®] skin and stringer are not deforming plastically and linear elastic fracture mechanics can be used for the prediction of the crack propagation. Finally, for cases that the crack in the adhesive layer propagated for more than 3.5 mm under high loads and long fatigue tests, it jumped through the aluminium in the glass/epoxy layers of the Glare[®] (Figure 6). These effects were not studied here. The

scatter of the experimental results, especially for Type I specimens, was considerable, reflecting the sensitivity of the testing to the material variability, cutting and preparation procedures.

Figure 6 Crack propagation for Type I specimen tested with a 2.5 mm maximum applied displacement for 500,000 cycles

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

A two dimensional Finite Element (FE) model was created in Abaqus[®]. Four-noded, bi-linear, plane strain, quadrilateral elements were used. Incompatible mode formulation was included in the model to enhance the bending behaviour of the elements. Non-linear geometric procedures were considered. For the FE model all plies of the Glare[®] material were modelled with one element per ply thickness, while two elements were used through the adhesive thickness. Materials were modelled as linear elastic. For the adhesive layer the properties in Table 3 were used, while for the Glare[®] the properties in Table 6 were used.

Table 6 Glare[®] constituent material properties [7]

Al 7475-T761			
$E = 70.3 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu = 0.33$	$\sigma_y = 448 \text{ MPa}$	
FM-94-27%-S2 Glass-187-460			
$E_1 = 53.7 \text{ GPa}$	$E_2 = 9.13 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{12} = 3.3 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{12} = 0.39$
FM-94-27%-S2 Glass-187-460			
$E_1 = 38.6 \text{ GPa}$	$E_2 = 8.27 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{12} = 4.14 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{12} = 0.26$

Verification of the FE model was performed by comparing the numerical calculations of the Type I specimens with the available experimental data. The linear elastic stiffness of the Type I specimens was calculated as 54.5 N/mm, which compares very well with the experimentally obtained, $54.4 \pm 1.5 \text{ N/mm}$ (Figure 7(a)). In addition the calculated strains on both the skin and the Z stringer compared very well with the measured ones, for these specific locations of the strain gauges (Figure 7(b)). This validates the use of the created model to simulate the crack growth in the adhesive layer.

Figure 7 (a) Experimental load-displacement curves and FE calculations for Type I specimens and (b) Calculated load vs. Strain on the skin and Z stringer compared to experimental data

Two methods were used to calculate G at the crack tip in the adhesive layer. First, a global energy balance between FE analysis of different incremental crack areas was used:

$$G = -dU/dA \quad (1)$$

where, U is the strain energy and A is the crack area. Because, G is a combination of Mode I (peel) and Mode II (in-plane shear) the value of G_{Total} can be broken down to G_I and G_{II} by using the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) technique. An initial crack of 0.03 mm was introduced in the adhesive layer. It was assumed that the crack, which was found to run in the adhesive interlayer (cohesive fracture), initiated due to stress concentration at the edge of the stringer. The conditions for initiation of the crack were not examined in this paper.

Figure 8 Normalised strain energy release rate vs. crack length for (a) Type I and (b) Type II specimens

Values of the strain energy release rate at the crack tip were obtained for various crack lengths. They are presented in Figure 8, normalised over the applied displacement (G/δ^2). From the $G - a$ plots in Figure 8 it can be seen that for both Type I and Type

II specimens the value of G_{Total} comprise 59% G_I and 41% G_{II} . The slope of the $G - a$ curve for the Type II specimens is negative, which means the crack will grow in a stable manner and possibly arrest. For Type I specimens the slope is nearly zero. This means that the crack will grow in a stable manner.

FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION

To derive fatigue life predictions a methodology described in [8] was followed. The strain energy release rate values at the crack tip were combined with the crack propagation data (fatigue crack growth material model) of the adhesive to yield the fatigue life prediction of the skin-stringer arrangements. The life prediction methodology was an iterative process. During this process an initial crack in the adhesive layer (e.g. 0.03 mm) was assumed and for any given applied displacement (loading) the values of G_I , G_{II} and G_{Total} were calculated at the crack tip from the FE model in Figure 8. Then, using the fatigue crack growth material models (Table 4) a fatigue crack growth rate, da/dN , is calculated and the number of cycles for the crack to grow up to 3.3 mm. For the fatigue life prediction the 95% prediction limits were used for both the crack growth material models (Mode I and Mixed Mode I/II). In this way a fatigue life prediction range is calculated. The results of the fatigue life prediction methodology are given in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Comparison of fatigue life prediction and experimental. (a) Type I specimens and Mode I material model, (b) Type I specimens and Mixed Mode I/II material model,

The correlation of the predicted fatigue life to the experimental data was not very satisfactory when a Mode I fracture material model alone was used, for both Type I and

Type II specimens. This was because there was a significant portion (41%) of G_{II} at the crack tip. When the Mixed Mode I/II material model was used, with $G_{II} / G_{Total} = 43\%$ the prediction improved, although the predictions were somewhat un-conservative. This is thought to be a factor of damage during the manufacture/cutting of the test specimens for the Type I specimens.

CONCLUSIONS

Experimental results and theoretical predictions of the fatigue life of two types of Glare[®] skin-stringer arrangements are presented in this paper. Finite element modelling and linear elastic fracture mechanics were used to evaluate the value of G at the crack tip in the adhesive layer between Glare[®] skin and stringers. The results were combined with material models describing the fatigue crack growth resistance of the adhesive and yield prediction of the fatigue. When the appropriate material model was used (Mixed Mode I/II crack growth model with $G_{II} / G_{Total} = 43\%$) satisfactory predictions were derived for the fatigue life. In general the predictions methodology over-predicted the fatigue life of the skin-stringer arrangements.

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REFERENCES

1. E. C. Botelho, R. A. Silva, L. C. Pardinia and M. C. Rezende, *Review on the Development and Properties of Continuous Fiber/epoxy/aluminum Hybrid Composites for Aircraft Structures*, Materials Research, 2006, **9**, 247-256
2. R. H. Martin, *Local Fracture Mechanics Analysis of Stringer Pull-Off and Delamination in a Post Buckled Compression Panel*, Applied Composite Materials, 1996, **3**, 249-264
3. R. Krueger, P. J. Minguet and T. K. O'Brien, *A Method for Calculating Strain Energy Release Rates in Preliminary Design of Composite Skin/Stringer Debonding Under Multi-Axial Loading*, Composite Structures: Theory and Practice, ASTM STP 1383, 2000, 105-128
4. R. Krueger, M. K. Cvitkovich, T. K. O'Brien and P. J. Minguet, *Testing and Analysis of Composite Skin/Stringer Debonding Under Multi-Axial Loading*, J. of Composite Materials, 2000, **34**, 1263-1300
5. L. F. M. da Silva, R. D. Adams and M. Gibbs, *Manufacture of Adhesive Joints and Bulk Specimens with High-Temperature Adhesives*, Int. Journal of Adhesion & Adhesives, 2004, **24**, 69-83
6. M. Samulak and J. Harris, *Effects of Mixed Mode Loading on the Durability of Structural Adhesive Joints*, Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Structural Adhesives in Engineering (SAEVII), 13th – 15th July 2004, Bristol, UK
7. J. Mancini, *Resistenza Statica e a Fatica Di Elementi Strutturali Realizzati in GLARE*, Tesi di Laurea in Ingegneria Aerospaziale, Università di Pisa, Facoltà di Ingegneria, Dipartimento di Ingegneria Aerospaziale 2006
8. R. H Martin, *Incorporating Interlaminar Fracture Mechanics into Design*, IMechE Conference Transactions of International Conference on Designing Cost-Effective Composites, 15th – 16th September 1998, London, UK